

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

TEACHERS' ATTITUDES TOWARDS THE IMPORTANCE OF DEVELOPING RESEARCH SKILLS AMONG HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

This article is devoted to the problem of developing research skills among high school students. This study aims to provide an insight into how teachers perceive the development of research skills among high school students. Particular attention is given to the influence how the formation of research skills and abilities becomes an integrative component of the pedagogical process in a modern school with the spread of the practice of conducting educational research by high school students.

Keywords: research skills, formation of research skills, research competence, foreign language education

Introduction

Performing the functions of a social institution of the twenty-first century, the modern school is focused on preparing each graduate for an informed choice of life path. The dynamically changing socio-economic situation requires young people to analyze the situation, engage in various activities, and, accordingly, the role of research skills and abilities increases. The formation of research skills at the senior level of school contributes to the expansion of individual cognitive experience and the formation of the research position of high school students.

Accordingly, the most important task of education at the present time is the development of research skills that are focused on the research activities of students. Involving students in research activities will allow them to learn how to invent, understand and master new things, express their own thoughts, be able to make decisions, formulate interests and realize opportunities.

Effective educational research develops not only research skills, but also learning skills in collaboration, communication, thinking (critical and problem-based thinking). The teacher must provide the necessary conditions for the development of research skills: purposefulness and consistency, creative environment, psychological comfort, motivation, personality of the teacher and consideration of age characteristics. The key point here is careful planning of the educational research. It is necessary to teach how to ask (formulate) scientific questions correctly, draw up a research plan, give priority to evidence, formulate conclusions (explanation) and link them with scientific knowledge. In order to this, the formation of research skills and abilities becomes an integrative component of the pedagogical process in a modern school with the spread of the practice of conducting educational research by high school students. In order to do this, a teacher today needs to own a large set of tools and methods for organizing research activities.

Therefore, the present study aims to investigate teachers' attitudes towards the importance of develop-

ing research skills among high school students. Specifically, this study addresses the following research questions:

1. Should development of research skills be incorporated in the classroom?
2. If yes, what research skills should be developed among high school students?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Definition of research skill

Research skills are considered as complex skills, since they include the simultaneous work of different psychological and theoretical ways of perception. Considering the concept of "research skills", it is impossible to give a clear definition. Both the components of this definition and the full definition of research skills are multifaceted and functional, and do not have one specific point of view.

V. N. Litovchenko defines research skills as a set of systematized knowledge, skills and abilities of a student, views and beliefs that determine functional readiness of a high school student for creative search solutions of cognitive tasks.

There are several approaches to the definition of "research skills": for example, V.V. Uspensky, I.A. Zimmaya and E.A. Shashenkova, N.L. Goloviznina and others consider research skills as a result and measure of research activity, i.e. as the ability to conduct independent observations, experiments acquired in the process of solving various kinds of research tasks. The authors of another approach, N.V. Sychkova, P.Yu. Romanov, M.N. Povolyaeva and others, consider research skills as the ability to take actions necessary to carry out research activities.

From the point of view of V.V. Uspensky, a research skill is "the ability of independent observations, experiments acquired in the process of solving research problems." The author also notes that "the skills of a researcher presuppose ... the ability to compare, analyze, isolate essential features, make generalizations and conclusions."

By general research skills, A.I. Savenkov understands the ability to see problems, ask questions, put

forward hypotheses, define concepts, classify, observe, conduct experiments, draw conclusions and conclusions, structure material, work with text, prove and defend their ideas.

According to P.V. Seredenko, research skills are an opportunity and its realization to perform a set of operations for the implementation of intellectual and empirical actions that make up research activities and lead to new knowledge.

The following approaches to the definition of the concept of "research skills" were outlined by G.V. Mukhamadiyarova:

- the ability of independent observations, experiments acquired in the process of solving research problems;
- possession of a complex system of mental and practical actions necessary for cognitive activity in all types of educational work;
- the ability to apply a particular research method in solving a given problem or research assignment;
- a system of intellectual and practical skills of educational work necessary for the independent performance of research or part of it.

Formation of research skills

Based on these scientific works, creatively working teachers strive to organize the research activities of schoolchildren in the practice of teaching. Since research activity is quite complex, it is studied in the vast majority of cases in adolescents. It is believed that younger students are not ready for it.

In this regard, an urgent problem today is teaching school children how to obtain and process scientific information through independent research activities within the competence approach. The competency-based approach in education is generally understood as an approach that focuses not on the content, but on the results of education expressed in the form of competencies (Azizov & Azizov, 2018). Research competence is interpreted by Aleksandrova and Sluchayna (2018) as the ability to conduct independent research and provide its results. Research competence is both the main task of the development of professional and methodological competence and a means of developing other professional, cultural and general competencies (Gorshkova, 2017).

Currently, the research function of professional activity is prioritized since it is linked to the growth of the teacher's research competence and results in high-quality student instruction. The issues surrounding the development of research competence are the focus of Mallaev's (2014) and Mura's (2012) research projects. The writings of Andreev (2012) and Kodjaspirov examine the theoretical underpinnings of this issue (2016).

The works of Avdeeva, Andrianova, and Nikulina take into account research activity in the context of professional pedagogical and sociological reflection (2014). Scientists from other countries are researching the unique characteristics of the development of research skills. Their research examines how each student's abilities change across online academic courses based on self-regulating research (Cohen & Baruth, 2017), focusing on how students' research skills are activated (Tuisk, 2008).

Bostrom & Sandberg provide insight into the challenge of creating professional activity kinds that take into account students' creative talents and the growth of their research independence (2009). Koletvinova & Bichurina take into account how research in the cognitive-integration direction is developing (2016).

Based on the creation of new information and its practical application, the research paradigm is seen as an essential part of the diverse human life (Larin, 2003; Andreev, 2012; Kiseleva, 2016).

METHODS

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative research method to identify the attitude of teachers to the development of research skills in high school students. This survey was conducted using an online questionnaire. The online questionnaire was prepared using Google Forms and distributed via social networks using the snowball method among the teaching staff from Almaty, Kazakhstan. The questionnaire was originally written in English.

Participants

The study involved 15 foreign language teachers who work with high school students. All of the participants are proficient in digital literacy; however, the objective may also be appropriate for individuals who are new to the teaching profession.

Table 1

Gender	Degree	Experience	Class
Female-13 (86.7%)	Undergraduate-4 (26.7%)	1-5 y.-10 (66.7%)	10 th - 13 (86.7%)
Male-2 (13.3%)	Master's-11 (73.3%)	5-10y.-4 (26.7%)	11 th - 5 (33.3%)
Prefer not to say	doctorate	10 or more - 1 (6.7%)	

Participant teachers' profiles show that most of the teachers' gender is female and most of them have master's degrees, which shows that they are aware of the methodology of FLT and its main conceptual basis. Most teachers' experiences vary from 1-5 years.

Instrument

The data were gathered by the researcher using an English-language questionnaire. Part 1 focused on revealing the importance of developing research skills (5

items), and Part 2 indicated specific research skills that teachers should develop in their educational process. The total number of items was 10, and they were separated into two sections (5 items). First, a Likert scale with five response options—strongly agree (1), agree (2), neutral (3), disagree (4), and strongly disagree (5)—was used. The second section of the survey consisted of multiple choice questions and a written format question that asked participants to choose specific research skills that high school students need to develop.

Research Procedure

Before beginning the study, the researchers developed the questionnaire, examined the pertinent literature, and assessed the validity of the tool. The questionnaire was sent to the intended respondents after it met the criteria. The complete privacy of all information submitted was again emphasized. After then, data analysis was performed after making sure the data were accurate. An investigation of instructors' attitudes toward acquiring particular research abilities was examined in order to provide a full pedagogical application.

RESULTS

Research question 1

Analysis on five scales was done in order to determine the average values of the teachers' responses to the question "Should development of research skills be incorporated in the classroom?". Results indicated in Table 2 showed positive viewpoint of teachers' attitudes by interpreting answers to the following questions:

Table 2

Participant Teachers' answers					
Questions	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1. The formation of research skills and abilities becomes an integrative component of the pedagogical process in a modern school with the spread of the practice of conducting educational research by high school students	6 (40%)	6 (40%)	1(10%)	1(10%)	-
2. Teachers should incorporate exercises on the development of research skills in their lessons.	7 (46.7%)	6(40%)	2(13.3%)	-	-
3.It is important to organize research activity in order to develop high school students' research skills in the educational process.	12(80%)	2(13.3%)	-	1 (6.7%)	-

Research question 2

The purpose of the second questionnaire was to find out what research skills should be developed among high school students. The results of the questionnaire indicated in Figure 1 shows that 10 teachers

think that creating effective research strategy skills (66.7%), and 9 teachers consider effectively communicating their arguments/thesis skills (60%) need to be developed.

What specific research skills high school students need to develop?

Figure 1

According to participants' answer in Table 3 listed research skill(s) which high school students need the most help with:

Table 3

1. Find appropriate information according to the topic
2. Analysis of information from different sources.
3. Analytical research skills
4. Selecting and analyzing relevant sources
5. Conducting various types of research as well as organizing data in various ways

Analyzing the answers of teachers, we can understand how important it is to develop students' analytical thinking and the ability to use the necessary literature for research. This proves that teachers should pay attention to the development of research skills in high school students.

Discussion

The primary purpose of the study was to identify the perceptions of teachers on the importance of developing research skills among high school students. As mentioned in literature review, the concept of research skill is quite complex. After analyzing the results of the questionnaire, teachers understand that developing research skills provides conditions for the productive development of their value, intellectual and creative potential, is a means of activating students, forming their interest in the studied material, allows them to significantly expand the scope of the studied material, forms subject and general skills. As N.I. Savenkov mentioned, the question of when students' own research began to be applied in educational practice has a clear and precise answer – they have always been used and have been in demand since ancient times, from the moment when the very need for learning manifested itself in the human community. The student always perceived some part of the information about the world reproductively from the elders, and mastered some independently, imitating adults, playing, exploring reality, while he had to observe, experiment and make his own conclusions and conclusions on this basis (Savenkov, 2010).

Throughout the study, teachers demonstrated favorable views toward the development of research skills such as identifying and finding appropriate information according to the topic. It can be proved by Ivashova O.A, she believes that research skills are understood as intellectual and practical skills due to the independent choice and application of methods and methods of research on materials available to students (Ivashova, 2009). Thus, it is suggested to help high school students develop these skills during the educational process.

Revealing the attitude of teachers on the development of research skills, it was found out that teachers have a positive attitude towards the use of exercises that develop specific research skills in their lessons including research activities. In order to this, Sokolova N.G that the key technological element in the development of research skills is a heuristic educational situation – a situation of activating ignorance, the purpose of which is the birth of a personal educational product by students (ideas, problems, hypotheses, versions, text). The methodology of developing research skills is based on open tasks that do not have unambiguous "correct" answers. Almost any element of research activity can be expressed in the form of an open task. (Sokolove, 2005)

Concluding, the current study has identified how teachers perceive research skills and whether it should be taught.

Conclusion

On the basis of research results, it can be concluded that there is a dire need to educate students and develop their research skills. One of the most important

tasks of our teachers is to educate a caring, active, thinking person. To do this, it is necessary to find additional forms of educational activity in which schoolchildren could take part on a voluntary basis — based on interest in a particular direction.

One of such forms is research activity, which is created with the aim of improving students' knowledge in a certain field of science, their acquaintance with the methods of scientific cognition; development of students' interests and abilities, acquisition of skills and abilities of search and research activities, as well as understanding the deep connection that exists between individual academic disciplines.

Thus, it can be concluded that research activity directly depends on the formation of the student's research skills. The acquisition of these skills directly depends on the actions performed by him through properly constructed work in the lesson. In order to build it correctly, the teacher must know what functions research skills have to develop the right actions, both in the scheduled work and in extracurricular activities. Only joint activity with the teacher during the entire study will give the student the opportunity to master new knowledge, skills and abilities, improve existing ones and master universal learning activities.

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